

INCENTIVE
CITIZEN SCIENCE HUBS

D3.1

Citizen Science Hubs' Pilot Operation Plans

Universitat Autònoma de
Barcelona (UAB)

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PROJECT INFORMATION

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D3.1: Citizen Science Hub Pilot Operation Plans

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VERSION CONTROL SHEET

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v0.3	27/05/2022	Elaborated draft with updates from partners' review	UAB
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Executive Summary

The document at hand is Deliverable (D) 3.1 “Citizen Science Hub’s Pilot Operation Plans”. The main purpose is to guide the partners in the planning of the pilot operation of their Citizen Science Hubs (CS Hubs), highlighting the key aspects to consider.

The key aspects of the CS Hubs’ pilot operation plans are the following:

- Objectives
- Set up of the CS Hubs
- Implementation of institutional changes
- Activities and tools to be piloted
- Stakeholders to be involved
- Processes for recruiting new participants and for retaining them
- KPIs, quality indicators and assessment criteria
- Timeline of the actions and roles of the pilot administrators
- Procedures, guidelines, and templates for interacting with participants and stakeholders

These key aspects are important to consider both for the pilot RPOs of the INCENTIVE project, but also for other RPOs interested in establishing a CS Hub in their own institutions.

1. Introduction

INCENTIVE is a three-year Horizon 2020 “Science with and for Society” project (Grant Agreement (GA) No 101005330) that brings together four Research Performing and Funding Organisations (RPFOs): the University of Twente, the Autonomous University of Barcelona, the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki and the Vilnius Gediminas Technical University. The project aims to stimulate them to embed Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) related institutional changes in their governance and operating model.

The key institutional change is the establishment of their own Citizen Science Hubs (CS Hubs). The CS Hubs will implement different types of activities with the aim of promoting Citizen Science (CS) in their organisations, including the start, support and/or dissemination of CS projects with and for their local stakeholder community.

The document at hand is Deliverable (D) 3.1 “Citizen Science Hub Pilot Operation Plans”, elaborated in the context of Task 3.1 “Citizen Science Hubs’ Pilot Operation Plans”. The main purpose is to guide the partners in the planning of the pilot operation of their CS Hubs, highlighting the key aspects to consider.

The remaining document consists of the following sections:

- **Section 2** articulates the overall approach followed to establish the bases for the design of the specific pilot operation plans.
- **Section 3** provides the reader guidance on the different key aspects to consider for the Pilot Operation Plans.
- **Section 4** presents an overview of the planned activities by each of the CS Hubs.
- **Section 5** provides some concluding remarks on the upcoming set up and operationalisation of the CS Hubs.

The **annexes** include the Outputs of the interactive session at the 3rd project meeting (Annex 1), the Guidelines to collect feedback for impact assessment and evaluation (by Q-PLAN) (Annex 2) and the Baseline RPFO report template elaborated by Q-PLAN and UAB (Annex 3).

2. Methodology

2.1 Overall approach

- **Step 1:** UAB created the structure of the Pilot Operation Plan deliverable, and shared it with the rest of the partners, to receive any suggestions for improvement.
- **Step 2:** To guide the partners in the design of their pilot operation plans, UAB, together with CC-CS, ECSA, Q-PLAN and UT, co-organised different meetings with the RPFOS' teams to allow them to think about different crucial aspects for the set up and the operationalisation of the CS Hubs, including a virtual interactive session at the 3rd project meeting, three virtual Mutual Learning Workshops (MLWs)¹, and a face-to-face workshop on the Pilot Operation Plans.
- **Step 3:** UAB considered the reports delivered at the end of March 2022, to identify the insights that are relevant for the elaboration of the pilot operation plans.
- **Step 4:** UAB collaborated with Q-PLAN in the creation of the RPFOS report template, with the aim of providing a useful tool for the pilot RPFOS to have a baseline on the institutional changes already in place in their organisations.

2.2 Virtual interactive session at the 3rd project meeting

Within the virtual 3rd project meeting, UT and UAB co-organised an interactive session targeted mainly at the RPFOS' teams (see Annex 1 for more details).

The main outcomes of the session were the following:

- Presentation of the Why? How? and What? of the CS Hubs of each pilot RPFOS
- Enhancement of the active listening skills of the participants, as they draw what they were listening on each of the CS Hubs
- Creation of two mood boards by CS Hub, one by the pilot RPFOS teams, and the other by the rest of the partners

2.3 1st Virtual Mutual Learning Workshop

The [1st Virtual MLW](#) focused on relevant aspects related to the Pilot Operation Plans, with the participation of the RPFOS teams.

The main outcomes of the MLW were the following:

- Presentation and discussion on the first ideas on the activities to be implemented by the CS Hubs during the pilot phase.
- Design of two possible events to be implemented by the CS Hubs during the pilot phase.

¹ Further information on these Mutual Learning Workshops will be available from September 2023 on in the D3.2 "Training and mutual learning".

2.4 2nd Virtual Mutual Learning Workshop

The [2nd Virtual MLW](#) focused on the design of the virtual presence of each of the CS Hubs, by allowing RPFOS teams to create a first draft design of the “About us” part of their future websites, covering:

- Strategy & Hub’s aspirations
- Organisation structure and people
- Website’s next steps and questions

After this exercise, the participants had the opportunity to participate in an interactive 1-hour session facilitated by Simona Cerrato, Communications and Community Manager at ECSA, on Ideas and tools for effective communication, focusing mainly on five key questions (Figure 1). And then, the RPFOS’ teams, together with Q-PLAN, ECSA, SDA Bocconi and CC-CS, created the first draft of an introductory text to describe their CS Hubs for the future website.

five questions

why communicate?

to whom?

why should they care?

how communicate?

what?

Source: Simona Cerrato (2022). Presentation on Ideas for effective communication during the INCENTIVE 2nd Mutual learning Workshop.

Figure 1: Five questions for an effective communication

2.5 Workshop on the Pilot Operation Plans

The Workshop on the Pilot Operation Plans had three main objectives:

- To ease the design process of the Pilot Operation Plans by the pilot RPFOS
- To get to know each other in person
- To get to know the facilities of the Design Lab in Twente

The main outcomes of the face-to-face meeting were the following:

- The pilot RPFOS received valuable information on the different services and activities offered by the Competence Center Citizen Science (CC-CS), jointly run by the University of Zurich and ETH Zurich, which could help the participants to design the pilot activities of their own CS Hubs.
- The pilot RPFOS got inspired by ECSA on the importance of equality, diversity and inclusiveness in Citizen Science.

- Q-PLAN presented the RPFO report template on the baseline of the already existing institutional changes at each of the pilot RPFOs.
- Each RPFO presented the timeline of the planned activities to be implemented during the pilot phase and got feedback from the rest of the participants.
- UT students interviewed each of the CS Hub's representatives from each RPFO to be able to create a visualisation of the different CS Hubs

2.6 3rd Virtual Mutual Learning Workshop

The [3rd Virtual MLW](#) focused on how to successfully design and run co-created CS projects. CC-CS facilitated a session based on the handbook they coordinated on this issue: [Practicing Citizen Science in Zurich. Handbook](#).

After a short theoretical part on the different phases of the design, implementation and evaluation of any CS project, CC-CS presented a real case to the INCENTIVE partners: Researchers from an NGO contacted CC-CS and presented them an issue they wanted to address with CS.

The participants of the MLW had to wear the hat of these researchers and design the CS project in groups, with the support of CC-CS, by covering the following aspects:

- Ideation
- Plan & Design
- Community Management

The participants of the workshop had a good overview of the whole process of implementation of a CS project, and could learn from the best practices and lessons learned by CC-CS when supporting researchers to apply CS.

3. Key aspects of the Pilot Operation Plans

3.1 Objectives

The objectives of each CS Hub differ from institution to institution, as they have different profiles. The research funding activities, experience in institutional change and the ecosystem of quadruple helix stakeholders and the existing structures promoting citizen engagement in science before the set-up of the CS Hubs, have an impact on the motivations for establishing a Citizen Science Hub, and the expected institutional changes to be implemented at each RPFO.

The long-term goals of the CS Hubs are in line with the INCENTIVE project objectives¹:

- O1. Grounding RRI in society
- O2. Transforming how RPFOs create impact and interact with their surroundings
- O3. Advancing sustainable development at the local, regional and global level

3.2 Set up of the CS Hubs

The first steps that each RPFO should carry out during the pilot phase are described in detail in the [D2.2 Citizen Science Hubs Governance Framework and Operating Models](#).

Each RPFO, considering their respective local context, will identify the facility to act as a single point of contact for citizen science at each organisation. Then, it is important that each RPFO has available human resources that will implement the activities of the CS Hub. And lastly, if the internal procedures allow this, each CS Hub should formulate the Board of Directors and the Stakeholder Board, which will be the formal decision-making body of the Citizen Science Hub.

3.3 Implementation of institutional changes

Each RPFO will be responsible for the implementation different institutional changes, depending not only on the needs that will be identified during the piloting phase, but also on their local enablers and barriers for institutional change. These institutional changes are presented in Table 1.

¹ See section 3.3 of the [D4.1 “Monitoring and Evaluation Framework”](#) for more details.

Table 1: Institutional changes and events

Institutional change	Institutional change event	Partners responsible for the planning of the institutional change event and for the related training and mutual learning	Partner responsible for the monitoring of the institutional change event
1. Enlargement of R&I activities by means of citizen science and civil society actors and citizens engagement.	1.1 Setup and operation of CS Hubs.	Planning: AUTH (T2.5), UAB (T3.1), each pilot RPFO Training and mutual learning: UZH (T3.2)	UAB (T3.3)
	1.2 CS Hubs Governance Structure Model.	Planning: UZH (T2.2), each pilot RPFO Training and mutual learning: UZH (T3.2)	UAB (T3.3)
	1.3 CS Hubs Operating Model.	Planning: UZH (T2.2), each pilot RPFO Training and mutual learning: UZH (T3.2)	UAB (T3.3)
	1.4 CS Hubs' participatory R&I activities.	Planning: UT (T2.4) and UAB (T3.1), each pilot RPFO Training and mutual learning: UZH (T3.2), UT (T2.4)	UAB (T3.3)
	1.5 Methodological guide and toolkit for setting up CS Hubs.	Planning: AUTH (T2.5) Training and mutual learning: UZH (T3.2), AUTH (T2.5)	UAB (T3.3)

Institutional change	Institutional change event	Partners responsible for the planning of the institutional change event and for the related training and mutual learning	Partner responsible for the monitoring of the institutional change event
	1.6 Action Plan & roadmap for the setup of CS Hubs.	Planning: UAB (T3.1), each pilot RPFO Training and mutual learning: UZH (T3.2)	UAB (T3.3)
2. Adoption of codes of conduct for RRI.	2.1 Code of conduct defining the rights and obligations of parties involved in the activities of the CS hubs, addressing ethical and legal considerations.	Planning: UZH (T2.2). each pilot RPFO Training and mutual learning: UZH (T3.2)	UAB (T3.3)
3. Streamlining of engagement with society for R&I decision making.	3.1 Memorandum of Collaboration of CS Hubs with quadruple helix stakeholders.	Planning: SDA Bocconi (T5.1), each pilot RPFO Training and mutual learning: UZH (T3.2)	UAB (T3.3) and SDA Bocconi (T5.1)
	3.2 CS Hub Stakeholder Board and Board of Directors.	Planning: UZH (T2.2), each pilot RPFO Training and mutual learning: UZH (T3.2)	UAB (T3.3)
	3.3 CS Hub Facilitator, Community Managers, Trainers.	Planning: UZH (T2.2), each pilot RPFO Training and mutual learning: UZH (T3.2)	UAB (T3.3)
4. Uptake of R&I standards for socially responsible, inclusive, sustainable R&I processes and products.	4.1 RRI regulations and standards across RRI keys.	Planning: Each pilot RPFO Training and mutual learning: UZH (T3.2)	UAB (T3.3)

Institutional change	Institutional change event	Partners responsible for the planning of the institutional change event and for the related training and mutual learning	Partner responsible for the monitoring of the institutional change event
	4.2 Adoption of the 10 Principles of Citizen Science.	Planning: Each pilot RPFO Training and mutual learning: UZH (T3.2)	UAB (T3.3)
	4.3 Research ethics & integrity regulations of CS Hub.	Planning: Each pilot RPFO Training and mutual learning: UZH (T3.2)	UAB (T3.3)
5. Adoption of a framework to anticipate the impacts of citizen science - driven R&I.	5.1 Citizen Science Hub societal, democratic, economic and scientific impact assessment methodology.	Planning: Q-PLAN (T4.1), each pilot RPFO Training and mutual learning: UZH (T3.2), Q-PLAN (T4.1)	UAB (T3.3)
6. Adoption of curricula that integrate science and society.	6.1 Development of capacity building content for active participation in citizen science.	Planning: UT (T2.4), AUTH (T2.5), UAB (T3.1), each pilot RPFO Training and mutual learning: UZH (T3.2)	UAB (T3.3)
7. Promotion of gender equality in RFPOs.	7.1 Adoption of gender balance measures about CS Hub staff power.	Planning: UZH (T2.2), each pilot RPFO Training and mutual learning: UZH (T3.2)	UAB (T3.3)
	7.2 Adoption of gender balance standards for participation in CS Hubs' activities.	Planning: UT (T2.4) and UAB (T3.1), each pilot RPFO Training and mutual learning: UZH (T3.2)	UAB (T3.3)

Institutional change	Institutional change event	Partners responsible for the planning of the institutional change event and for the related training and mutual learning	Partner responsible for the monitoring of the institutional change event
	7.3 Adoption of Inclusive incentivisation methodology for participation in CS Hubs.	Planning: SDA Bocconi (T2.3), each pilot RPFO Training and mutual learning: UZH (T3.2) and SDA Bocconi (T2.3)	UAB (T3.3)
8. Fostering of open science and open access to scientific results and data.	8.1 Open access provisions for the operation of CS Hubs (e.g., use of open data repositories, open source software, etc.).	Planning: Each pilot RPFO Training and mutual learning: UZH (T3.2)	UAB (T3.3)
9. Activation of a mutual learning process across stakeholders of the local ecosystem.	9.1 Material for stakeholders' capacity building	Planning: Each pilot RPFO Training and mutual learning: UZH (T3.2)	UAB (T3.3)
	9.2 Framework for Stakeholders' Mutual learning	Planning: Each pilot RPFO Training and mutual learning: UZH (T3.2)	UAB (T3.3)

Institutional change	Institutional change event	Partners responsible for the planning of the institutional change event and for the related training and mutual learning	Partner responsible for the monitoring of the institutional change event
	9.3 Methodology for engagement of Quadruple Helix Actors.	Planning: SDA Bocconi (T2.3), each pilot RPFO Training and mutual learning: UZH (T3.2)	UAB (T3.3)
10. New partnerships for RRI across RPFOs.	10.1 Memorandum of Collaboration between CS Hubs.	Planning: SDA Bocconi (T5.1), each pilot RPFO Training and mutual learning: UZH (T3.2)	UAB (T3.3) and SDA Bocconi (T5.1)
	10.2 Network of Interest in institutionalisation of CS Hubs and grounding RRI in regional communities.	Planning: ECSA (T5.2), each pilot RPFO Training and mutual learning: UZH (T3.2)	UAB (T3.3), ECSA (T5.2)

While planning and implementing these institutional changes and/or others, the pilot RPFOS can consider the insights and recommendations provided by the H2020 Time4CS project. In particular, Herrera and Haklay (2022), present a knowledge-based framework in support of Citizen Science, to be implemented by RPFOS aiming at enhancing the role of citizen science in their institutions, and a proposed chronology of institutional transformation (Figure 2).

Source: Abril Herrera, & Muki Haklay. (2022). D1.3: Lessons learnt repository of TIME4CS (g1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6402091>

Figure 2: Chronology of institutional transformation

The chronology can also be interpreted as a virtuous circle, as the institutional transformation will most likely lead to an increase of diverse disciplinary contributions of CS projects (Figure 3).

To plan the institutional changes to be implemented by each RPFOS, it is very helpful to carry out a baseline analysis of the current institutional changes in place. For that, RPFOS can use the RPFOS template available in Annex 3.

Source: Adapted from Abril Herrera, & Muki Haklay. (2022). D1.3: Lessons learnt repository of TIME4CS (g1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6402091>

Figure 3: Institutional transformation virtuous circle

3.4 Pilot activities and tools

The pilot activities that each CSH is going to implement during the pilot phase of the project are the following:

- **R&I and co-creation activities:** Each CSH should support the implementation of at least 2 citizen science projects. Other R&I and co-creation activities include (i) designing, setting the agenda and/or managing the RPF0's R&I programmes, (ii) setting-up, managing and implementing R&I activities according to their needs (e.g., co-creation of public policies, evaluation of research proposals applying for funding or other R&I funding decisions, etc.).
- **Awareness-raising activities:** Possible activities include identifying target audiences, developing content (videos, concise texts, games, etc.), and distributing them through the most suitable channels (e.g., website, social media, newsletter, blogs, flyers, Network of Interest, other synergizing networks, etc.); and organising face-to-face or virtual events, such as Launch Events or InfoDays.
- **Mutual-learning activities and networking:** The Citizen Science Hubs will organise several mutual learning activities (webinars, digital meetings, etc.) with a view to enabling the stakeholders of the

Citizen Science Hubs to connect and exchange knowledge with stakeholders from other similar initiatives.

- **Capacity building activities:** The Citizen Science Hubs will offer their communities a variety of opportunities to be involved in science, with a view to creating pathways for communities to be actively involved in scientific knowledge development and improve the capacity of participants to creatively contribute to R&I. The capacity building activities can also target researchers, teachers, and/or representatives from civil society, the private and the public sector, with the aim of training them on how to apply and promote citizen science.
- **Monitoring & Evaluation** activities to collect sufficient evidence for the assessment and evaluation of the INCENTIVE activities and impact. A guide on the Monitoring and Evaluation activities has been elaborated by Q-PLAN (see Annex 2) to facilitate the implementation of the monitoring and evaluation activities by the RPFOS during the pilot phase.

Each CSH will define the activities that they are going to implement, taking into account the recommendations of [D2.4 “Activities of Citizen Science Hubs”](#) by the University of Twente. To design the activities, mainly the ones related to the involvement of citizens in CS projects, the RPFOS can consult the resources available at [eu-citizen.science](#) and at the [Citizen Science Toolkit](#) developed by the H2020 SwafS [CiteSHealth project](#), and adapt them to their local context. Furthermore, INCENTIVE partners are considering the possibility of working collaboratively and co-designing some of the activities, to be then adapted and implemented at each of the pilot RPFOS.

3.5 Stakeholders to be involved

Stakeholders involved in the Citizen Science Hubs’ decision making and activities can be both internal and external to the RPFOS:

- Internal stakeholders can be non-academic staff, undergraduate and master’s students, PhD students and academic staff.
- External stakeholders can be representatives of public bodies, industry, civil society organisations, citizens, or the academia, including members of other RPFOS, research centres, and other education-related institutions.

3.6 Processes for recruiting new participants and retaining them

Each CSH will define their own processes for recruitment and engagement of participants, taking into account the specificities of each target group. To do so, there are some useful insights that they can consider. To start with, in [D6.1 “Stakeholder engagement, Dissemination and Communication Plan”](#), White Research (WR) presented the INCENTIVE target audience categories (Table 1) and the INCENTIVE baseline messages per Quadruple Helix stakeholder group (Table 2). Related to the recruitment of participants in citizen science projects and to the maintenance of citizen’s engagement towards the end of the project, SDA Bocconi has provided the RPFOS with some incentivisation tools in [D2.3 “Manual for Citizen Science Community Building”](#). In addition, each RPFOS should design and implement their awareness raising activities bearing in

mind that these activities can be an opportunity to reach potential participants in the other type of activities the CS Hubs aim to implement.

Both the implementation teams and the CS Project leaders should monitor the gender balance in the participation in the CS Hub's and in the CS project's activities. In case of identifying a gender disbalance in the participation, they should adopt standards for gender balance in the planned activities.

3.7 KPIs, quality indicators and assessment criteria

Each RPFO will take into account the KPIs, indicators and assessment criteria established in the Grant Agreement (GA) and in [D4.1 "Monitoring & Evaluation Framework"](#) by Q-PLAN. The most important KPIs and achievement indicators to consider during the set-up and operation of the CS Hubs are the ones presented in the following tables.

Table 2: INCENTIVE KPIs related to the Set-up and operation of the CSHs

KPI	Assessment criteria	Definition	Data source
KPI-1 Citizen Science Hubs launched to ensure the better and more sustainable engagement with citizens and society as a whole	4	<p>There is a single point of contact for citizen science at each of the pilot RPFOS.</p> <p>The Citizen Science Hubs are implementing activities to promote citizen science.</p>	RPFO report
KPI-2. Number of activities with greater involvement in citizen science	8 (2 per CS Hub)	Implementation of capacity building activities and/or CS project activities	Indicators O1A1.3, O26.1, O26.4 of the CS Hub report available in D4.1
KPI-3. Members of society participating in decision making within the Citizen Science Hubs	>100	<p>Sum of:</p> <p>1-Members of society participating in the co-creation workshop of the CS Hubs</p> <p>2- Members of society participating in the decision-making bodies of the CS Hubs</p> <p>3- Members of society participating in the Action Plan Co-creation Workshops for ensuring the sustainability of the institutional changes within the RPFOS.</p> <p>4- Members of society participating in decision-making related to any activity, space or infrastructure funded by the RPFOS</p> <p>5-Members of society participating in the decision-making aspects of citizen science projects, such as the identification of</p>	<p>See Table 3: Changes proposed to the Monitoring and Evaluation methods</p> <p>Each RPFO's assistance lists to the events</p>

		<p>citizen’s concerns, the translation of this concern into a research question, the design of the study to answer the research question, the governance model of the project establishing how decisions are made during the project development, and the co-creation and planning of actions that can generate recognition of the issue explored.</p>	
KPI-4. Stakeholders’ interest in engaging in science	>+40%	Perceived percentage increase in stakeholders' interest in engaging in science as a result of participating in CS Hub activities (on average)	Indicator O3B4.4 considered in the Event Questionnaire available in D4.1 CS Hub Report available in D4.1
KPI-6. Increase in scientific literacy of stakeholders engaged in citizen science	>+40%	<p>Average of:</p> <p>1-Number of citizens who reported that in the future they would more actively search information about relevant technologies and scientific outputs or read related articles and news / Total number of citizens in CS projects surveyed</p> <p>2-Number of citizens reported that they gained a better understanding of how research is performed / Total number of citizens in CS projects surveyed</p> <p>3-Number of citizens who reported gaining sufficient knowledge from the above capacity building activities to be able participate in CS projects / Total number of citizens surveyed</p>	<p>Indicators O1B1.5, O1B1.6, considered in the CS Project Questionnaire (Participant) and indicator O26.3 considered in the Event Questionnaire for stakeholders who participated in capacity-building events available in D4.1</p> <p>CS Hub report available in D4.1</p>
KPI-7. Stakeholders perceiving benefits from higher relevance of scientific outputs	> 60%	Number of stakeholders who perceive CS as a way to produce scientific outputs that are highly relevant to local societies needs / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	Indicator O3B4.3 considered in the Event Questionnaire available in D4.1 CS Hub report available in D4.1

KPI-8. Stakeholders perceiving benefits from improved research results as social demands are addressed	> 60%	Number of stakeholders who perceive CS as a way to achieve better research results that can address social demands / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	Indicator O3B4.2 considered in the Event Questionnaire available in D4.1 CS Hub report available in D4.1
KPI-9. Acceptance of Citizen Science as a legitimate way of doing research	> 80% acceptance	Number of stakeholders perceiving CS as a legitimate way of doing research / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	Indicator O3B4.1 considered in the Event Questionnaire available in D4.1 CS Hub report available in D4.1
KPI-13. New mechanisms for meaningful public engagement in RPFOs	10	Number of new mechanisms for meaningful interactions between RPFOs and their stakeholder ecosystem This includes the implementation of the institutional changes mentioned in Table 1 Institutional changes and events.	RPFO report
KPI-14. Public engagement activities in the funding mechanisms of RPFOs	>4	Co-definition, validation, selection/or execution of funded activities by the University with key stakeholders.	Identifier O23.1 of the CS Hub Report available in D4.1
KPI-15. Number of actions for creating new pathways for contributing to SDGs	96	Institutional change events mentioned in Table 1 Institutional changes and events.	RPFO report
KPI-16. Sustainable and impactful institutional changes supported by the project	>10	Institutional changes mentioned in Table 1 Institutional changes and events.	RPFO report

Table 3: INCENTIVE achievement indicators related to the Set-up and operation of the CSHs

Achievement indicator	Assessment criteria	Definition	Data source
R&I co-creation activities pursued by Citizen Science Hubs	6	R&I co-creation activities, such as co-definition of research questions, implementation of CS projects, peer review, co-evaluation of R&I proposals, co-production of R&I content, agenda setting in R&I, co-design of R&I programmes.	Identifiers O21.1 and O2.3.1 of the CS Hub report available in D4.1
Participants in activities enhancing scientific literacy	120 - 200 / 30 - 50 per CS Hub	Participants in capacity building activities aiming at increasing knowledge on science and citizen science.	Identifier O26.1 of the CS Hub report available in D4.1
Operational Citizen Science Hubs	4	There is a single point of contact for citizen science at each of the pilot RPFOs	RPFO report
Number of citizen science projects and R&I activities with engaged roles for all R&I stakeholders	>8 / 2 per Citizen Science Hub	2 Citizen Science projects implemented in each pilot RPFO, with the support of the CS Hubs. Other R&I activities with engaged roles for all R&I stakeholders will also be considered.	Identifier O21.1 of the CS Hub report available in D4.1
Internal participants (researchers, professors, students, etc)	80	Non-academic staff, undergraduate and master's students, PhD students and academic staff	See Table 4: Changes proposed to the Monitoring and Evaluation methods

External participants across the quadruple helix (citizens, policy makers, business, other RPFOs, etc)	80	Representatives of public bodies, industry, civil society organisations, citizens, or the academia	See Table 4: Changes proposed to the Monitoring and Evaluation methods
Institutional changes stimulated by INCENTIVE	10	Institutional changes mentioned in Table 1 Institutional changes and events	RPFO report
Institutional change events	96 / 24 per CS Hub	Institutional changes events mentioned in Table 1 Institutional changes and events	RPFO report

3.8 Timeline of the actions and Roles of the pilot administrators

A timeline of the actions planned from January 2022 to September 2023 is provided below, considering both the set-up of the Citizen Science Hub and the implementation of the activities.

Figure 4: Timeline of the INCENTIVE Set-up and Operation of the CS Hubs

Within each of the pilot operation plans, a timeline of the actions and roles of the pilot administrators will be defined.

3.9 Procedures, guidelines, and templates for interacting with participants and stakeholders

3.9.1 Procedures, guidelines, and templates for interacting with participants and stakeholders

Each RPFO will adapt the procedures, guidelines and templates for interacting with participants and stakeholders provided in the Monitoring and Evaluation Framework of the project (D4.1) to their local languages and add any specific needs during the pilot phase. By doing so, the RPFOs will be able to collect feedback on the piloted activities. To be able to monitor some achievement indicators during the implementation of the activities, some changes to the templates provided by Q-PLAN are proposed, as specified in Table 4.

Table 4: Proposed changes to the Monitoring and Evaluation methods

Related KPIs or Achievement indicators	Methods	D4.1 proposal	Proposed change	Justification
<p>Internal participants across the quadruple helix (researchers, professors, students, etc)</p> <p>External participants across the quadruple helix (citizens, policy makers, business, other RPFOs, etc)</p>	<p>Event Questionnaire</p>	<p>You participated in this event as a member of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • academia or research/education • governmental body / regional authority • business • civil society organisation (such as an NGO representative) • local community • other (please specify) 	<p>You participated in this survey as a member of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • non-academic staff of [pilot RPFO] • undergraduate and master's students of [pilot RPFO] • PhD students of [pilot RPFO] • academic staff of [pilot RPFO] • academia or research/education other than [pilot RPFO] • governmental body / regional authority (O1C1.4) • business (O1C1.2) • civil society organisation (such as NGO representative) (O1C1.3) • local community • other (please specify) 	<p>To be able to distinguish between internal and external participants in events</p>

<p>Internal participants (researchers, professors, students, etc)</p> <p>External participants across the quadruple helix (citizens, policy makers, business, other RPFOs, etc)</p>	<p>CS Project Questionnaire & CS Project Questionnaire (Leader)</p> <p>MSC Interview Template</p>	<p>You participated in this survey as a member of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • academia or research/education • governmental body / regional authority (O1C1.4) • business (O1C1.2) • civil society organisation (such as NGO representative) (O1C1.3) • local community • other (please specify) 	<p>You participated in this survey as a member of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • non-academic staff of [pilot RPFO] • undergraduate and master's students of [pilot RPFO] • PhD students of [pilot RPFO] • academic staff of [pilot RPFO] • academia or research/education other than [pilot RPFO] • governmental body / regional authority (O1C1.4) • business (O1C1.2) • civil society organisation (such as NGO representative) (O1C1.3) • local community • other (please specify) 	<p>To be able to distinguish between internal and external participants in CS projects and in the MSC approach</p>
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<p>KPI-3. Members of society participating in decision making within the Citizen Science Hubs</p> <p>Achievement indicators R&I Activities</p>	<p>CS Project Questionnaire (Leader)</p>	<p>How many citizens were involved in the following CS project activities? <i>Please provide the data below.</i></p> <p>1-O1A4.1 data collection</p> <p>2-O1A4.2 co-definition of research questions/theme of study</p> <p>3-O1A4.3 data analysis or cleaning</p> <p>4-O1A4.4 validation of the output</p> <p>5-O1A4.5 extraction of conclusions</p>	<p>How many citizens were involved in the following CS project activities? <i>Please provide the data below.</i></p> <p>1-O1A4.1 data collection</p> <p>2-O1A4.2 co-definition of research questions/theme of study (including identification of citizen's concerns)</p> <p>3- design of the study to answer the research question</p> <p>4- debate on the governance model of the project establishing how decisions are made during the project development</p> <p>5-O1A4.3 data analysis or cleaning</p> <p>6-O1A4.4 validation of the output</p> <p>7-O1A4.5 extraction of conclusions</p> <p>8- co-creation and planning of actions that can generate recognition of the issue explored</p>	<p>To be able to identify the members of society participating in the decision-making aspects of citizen science projects (answers 2, 3, 4 and 8)</p>
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3.9.2 Report on the successes and the issues faced

In addition, the RFOs will report to the consortium on the successes and the issues faced during the pilot phase using the [Lessons Learned Database](#), only available for INCENTIVE consortium partners, including the following aspects, among others:

- Partner
- Description of the success or the issue faced
- Causes of the success or the issue faced
- Good practices and lessons learned
- Measures to consider the good practices and the lessons learned for the implementation of future activities and actions
- Impact of the success or the issue faced

The possibility to create a forum topic of discussion related to the successes and good practices on the Citizen Science discussion forum developed by AUTH will be considered, to have a common space to share and exchange on our experiences with more detail. And UAB will identify the successes and issues faced that are useful to be explained among the partners, and, together with UZH, organise mutual learning events to enable a space for this.

Furthermore, the possibility of adding new CS-related tools to the [Citizen Science Toolkit](#) developed within the H2020 SwafS [CitieSHealth project](#) will be considered. This would have two key goals: to give visibility to the best practices implemented by the INCENTIVE partners, and to contribute to the sustainability of the platform.

4. Pilot CS Hub's Pilot Operation Plans

Each of the pilot RPFO will finish the elaboration of their specific CS Hub Pilot Operation Plans considering the guidelines of the current deliverable¹. The plans will be completed by September 2022 marking the start of the piloting phase. They might be adapted to answer to current needs and expectations, together with the formal decision-making bodies of each CS Hub.

In Table 5, an overview of the provisional planned activities of the RPFOs is given. There are some activities that are very similar among the RPFOs, and others that have different approaches. This enables the INCENTIVE partners to consider the possibility of co-designing together activities that more than one partner aims to carry out, to adapt them to their respective local context and to implement them. Furthermore, the pilot RPFOs can learn from the experience of the different types of activities that each of the RPFOs implement during the pilot phase.

¹ The specific Pilot Operation Plans for each RPFO will be available upon request from September 2022 on.

Table 5: Planned activities of the CS Hubs

Type of activity	UT	UAB	AUTh	VG TU
R&I and co-creation activities	<p>1-Co-creation of the CSH</p> <p>2-Co-creation of >1 CS projects</p> <p>3-Open call to the public to engage in deciding on research (funding)</p>	<p>1-Support in the implementation of the Citizen Science project “Empowering urban cyclists through citizen science”</p> <p>2-Support in the implementation of a Citizen Science project “Citizen Arenas for Improved Environmental Quality & Resource Use in SMART-ER cities”</p> <p>3-Workshop on transformative innovation labs and shared agendas</p>	<p>1- CS Project 1: Data collection activity</p> <p>2- CS Project 2: Knowledge flow and exchange</p>	<p>1-Co-creation workshop with LibOCS and TIME4CS projects</p> <p>2-Co-creation workshop with Catalysta Ventures</p>
Awareness-raising activities	<p>1-Citizen Science conference on May 12, 2022</p>	<p>1-Launch Event</p>	<p>1-Awareness raising activity at city scale</p> <p>2-Awareness raising activity(ies) at AUTh scale</p>	<p>1-Participation in Open Government Week</p> <p>2-Preparation of dissemination and training material on principles of Citizen Science, RRI and Open Science in Lithuanian language</p>
Mutual learning activities and networking	<p>1-Cross-fertilisation between CS projects</p>	<p>1-UAB Citizen Science Community mutual learning and networking meetings</p>	<p>1-Physical workshop on best practices on how to run a CS activity</p>	<p>1-Series of Brown bag seminars at Vilnius Tech</p>

Type of activity	UT	UAB	AUTH	VG TU
Capacity building activities	1-CS lunch sessions with researchers and students 2-CS training for researchers, students and non-scientists	1-Citizen Science training for PhD students 2-Citizen Science training for high school teachers	1-Map the CS Activities of AUTH 2-Meeting with local quadruple helix stakeholders and discuss collaboration schemes as well as their priorities concerning common CS activities and project	1-Training “The basics of citizen science” in cooperation with Lithuanian Citizen Science Association 2-Training for PhD students “Responsible PhD: RRI and PhD Research Projects”
Monitoring and Evaluation activities	1-Collect information on institutional changes and fill in the RPFO report 2-Collect feedback from the CS Hub activities’ participants and fill in the CS Hub report 3-Collect feedback from the CS projects’ leaders and CS projects’ participants 4-Set target values for each indicator 5-Interview stakeholders (also contributing to Most Significant Change) 6-Present results to stakeholders and get their feedback (through Task 5.1)			

5. Conclusion

In this report, the key aspects of the CS Hubs pilot operation plans have been presented:

- Objectives
- Set up of the CS Hubs
- Implementation of institutional changes
- Activities and tools to be piloted
- Stakeholders to be involved
- Processes for recruiting new participants and for retaining them
- KPIs, quality indicators and assessment criteria
- Timeline of the actions and Roles of the pilot administrators
- Procedures, guidelines, and templates for interacting with participants and stakeholders

These key aspects are important to consider both for the pilot RPFOS of the INCENTIVE project, but also for other RPFOS interested in establishing a CS Hub in their own institutions.

Furthermore, the overview of the planned activities of the pilot RPFOS have been represented, to give some specific examples of activities which could be also adapted and implemented in other CS Hubs created by other RPFOS.

The next step for the pilot RPFOS is to start the pilot phase, by setting up their CS Hubs and starting to implement the pilot activities they have planned, together with the needed institutional changes. During the pilot phase, mutual learning events will take place to allow the exchange of best practices and lessons learned.

6. Annexes

Annex 1: Outputs of the interactive session at the 3rd project meeting

UT's CS Hub outputs of the interactive session at the 3rd project meeting

Figure 1: UT's CS Hub's Why? How? What?

Figure 2: UT's CS Hub's mood board 1

Figure 3: UT's CS Hub's mood board 2

UAB's CS Hub outputs

Figure 1: UAB's CS Hub's Why? How? What?

Note: The circle in the middle represents the CS Hub, the circles around represent the different resources and facilities available at the University, and the squares represent the facilities available outside of the University. The main idea is that the CS Hub will connect all these resources and facilities, interacting with the 4H in the framework of the Hub B-30.

Figure 2: UAB's CS Hub's mood board 1

Figure 3: UAB's CS Hub's mood board 2

AUTH's CS Hub outputs

Figure 1: AUTH's CS Hub's Why? How? What?

Figure 2: AUTH's mood board 1

Figure 3: AUTH's mood board 2

VG TU's CS Hub outputs

Figure 1: VG TU's CS Hub's Why? How? What?

Figure 2: VGTU's mood board 1

Figure 3: VGTU's mood board 2

Annex 2: Guidelines to collect feedback for impact assessment and evaluation

The document at hand aims to guide the four INCENTIVE RPFOS to monitor and evaluate their activities and impact. In other words, the document explains the RPFOS' remaining contribution in Work Package 4 (Task 4.2 and Task 4.3) and provides some tips for smooth implementation.

First, each RPFOS needs to appoint a person to coordinate the INCENTIVE data collection (aka monitoring) activities within the RPFOS. We suggest that this role is undertaken by the CS Hub secretary or any other person with similar responsibilities within the CS Hub. Then, the RPFOS needs to undertake the following activities:

Activity 1: Collect information on institutional changes and fill in the RPFOS report

📅 M16 – M18 (May – July 2022), M23 (Dec 2022), and M31 (Aug 2023)

The RPFOS report aims to monitor the institutional changes and institutional change events that each RPFOS considers and/or pilots. The Hub Secretary needs to collect the required data, fill in the report and share it with the T4.2 leader (VGTU) in three instances: M16 – M18 (May - July 2022), M23 (Dec 2022), and M31 (Aug 2023). The respective data need also be uploaded to the reporting database by the Hub Secretary to facilitate data utilisation by other partners. The template (available in Annexe 3 of the deliverable 3.1) is quite generic and includes all the relevant indicators that the RPFOS needs to monitor. The CS Hub secretary is welcome to adjust the report by adding new indicators. Finally, any indicators that the RPFOS did not manage to monitor should be clearly signified, thus providing a view of potentially problematic indicators or issues that are more appropriate for the qualitative method (i.e., stakeholder interviews).

Activity 2: Collect feedback from the CS Hub activities' participants and fill in the CS Hub report

📅 M23 (Dec 2022), M27 (Apr 2023), and M31 (Aug 2023)

The CS Hub report aims to monitor the various activities the CS Hubs organise, including R&I co-creation activities (e.g., R&I agenda setting), capacity building workshops, and mutual learning events. The CS Hub Secretary seeks feedback from these activities' participants, aggregates their responses into a CS Hub report and shares the report with the T4.2 leader (VGTU) in three instances: M23 (Dec 2022), M27 (Apr 2023), and M31 (Aug 2023). The respective data need also be uploaded to the reporting database by the Hub Secretary to facilitate data utilisation by other partners. The report template (available in Annexe 5 of the D4.1) is quite generic and includes all the indicators that a CS Hub needs to monitor. However, the Hub secretary is welcome to adapt the report to the need and purposes of the specific CS Hub. Finally, an event questionnaire has been prepared (available in Annexe 6 of D4.1). The CS Hub Secretary has the option to modify and use that questionnaire to capture the data required for the CS Hub report.

Activity 3: Collect feedback from the CS projects leaders and participants

📅 By the end of the CS project or at M31 (i.e., Aug 2023)

Each CS project needs to appoint the role of "CS project leader" to a person, being either a researcher or any other type of stakeholder. In Annexes 3 and 4 of D4.1, there are two questionnaires available. They shall be

used to capture feedback from the participants of each CS project and the CS project leader. Both questionnaires should be filled in by the end of the CS project or at M31 (i.e., Aug 2023), at the latest. In collaboration with the Hub Secretary, the CS project leader is responsible for collecting answers from both questionnaires. Then, the CS Hub Secretary aggregates and anonymises the data and uploads it to a dedicated reporting database.

Activity 4: Set target values for each indicator

M21 (Oct 2022)

Initially, Q-PLAN will investigate the baseline situation in each RPFO for a subset of crucial indicators, considering information from previous deliverables. Then, Q-PLAN will create the first draft of potential/suggested targets for each of these indicators. Particular attention will be paid to making the target values of all indicators specific, measurable, achievable, relevant and time-bound. Afterwards, the RPFOs will be invited to comment and adjust the target values, considering their realistic circumstances and available resources. The final draft of the targets will be shared with Q-PLAN by M21 (Oct 2022).

Activity 5: Interview stakeholders (contributing also to Most Significant Change)

M31 (Aug 2023)

In M31 (Aug 2023), when the CS Hub activities are almost completed, the RPFOs will interview four internal or external stakeholders (1 per stakeholder group) based on a semi-structured questionnaire developed by Q-PLAN. The questionnaire will serve both monitoring (T4.2) and evaluation purposes (T4.3). In particular:

- in the first part of the interview, the stakeholder will be asked to tell their personal stories of how they experienced the most significant change taking place within the RPFO (the Most Significant Change approach).
- In the second part of the interview, the interviewer will briefly present to the stakeholder the progress expedited towards our project objectives, mentioning specifically the CS projects conducted and the institutional changes implemented within the RPFO. Then, each stakeholder will opine on the impact and significance of those activities, based on their expectations of the project.

Accounting for time and human resource constraints, if a face-to-face interview is not possible, the questionnaire can be shared with the survey subject via email to be filled in asynchronously. Finally, while the questionnaire template is in English, it is the prerogative of the CS Hub to translate the questionnaires to their native language. The results should be communicated directly to the T4.2 leader (VGTU) in English and uploaded to the reporting database by the Hub Secretary.

Activity 6: Present results to stakeholders and get their feedback (through Task 5.1)

M32 (Sep 2023)

In M32 (Sep 2023), when the CS Hub activities are completed, the RPFOs, as part of their work for Task 5.1, will present their results to stakeholders in a dedicated workshop. The purpose is to illustrate the achieved institutional changes and their substantial societal, democratic, economic and scientific impact. Representatives from the partner RPFO's main decision-making bodies (university council, rectorate, etc.), CS Hub Stakeholder Board members, and other key stakeholders will be invited. Following the presentation,

stakeholders will be asked to provide their feedback on the performance and impact of the INCENTIVE activities through a questionnaire developed by Q-PLAN in Task 4.3. The respective data need also be uploaded to the reporting database by the Hub Secretary to facilitate data utilisation by other partners.

Annex 3: Baseline RPFO report template

This report aims to capture and regularly monitor the integration of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) practices into the Research Performing and Funding Organisations (RPFOs) of the INCENTIVE project. Each CS Hub's Secretary needs to collect the required data and fill in the report in three instances: M16-M18 (May – July 2022), M23 (Dec 2022), and M31 (Aug 2023). The respective data must also be uploaded to the [reporting database](#) by the Hub Secretary to facilitate data utilisation by other partners.

What is the name of the RPFO?

- Universiteit Twente (UT)
- Universidad Autonoma de Barcelona (UAB)
- Aristotelio Panepistimio Thessalonikis (AUP)
- Vilniaus Gedimino Technikos Universitetas (VGTU)

1. (O27.6) Does your RPFO take any actions and implement any standards or **policies to minimise gender inequality** within its governance framework and research activities (e.g., requirements for equal representation of both genders in decision-making bodies)? If yes, then what is it?

2. (O22.1) Does your RPFO have a **Code of Conduct**, meaning a policy that outlines principles and standards that all employees and researchers must follow? If yes, how many of the following elements are included: ethical principles, values, accountability, standard of conduct, standard of practice, and disciplinary actions? *UZH mentions these elements as the most common elements to include in a code of conduct. So, you may read Deliverable 2.2 and/or contact UZH for further information.*

3. (O25.2) Does your RPFO set in place any process to monitor and evaluate the societal, democratic, economic and scientific **impact of its research activities**? For instance, does it require or support its researchers (or CS project leaders) to anticipate and assess the impact of their research design and potential research outcomes on society, environment and economy?

4. (O24.2) Does your RPFO have in place any dedicated body or **mechanism to safeguard ethical standards** (e.g., a research ethics committee or a research integrity office). If yes, then what is it?

5. (O28.2) Does your RPFO have in place **open-access policies** or some institutional mechanism (e.g., incentives) for promoting open science? If yes, then what is it? *Please consider access to data, publications and pieces of software.*

6. (O24.4) Does your RPFO have any formal processes or provisions for **sharing information with the public** about ongoing or completed research activities? If yes, then what exactly?

7. Please indicate which of the following institutional change events (foreseen by the GA) you have implemented.

Institutional change event	Done?
• 1.1 Setup and operation of CS Hubs.	
• 1.2 CS Hubs Governance Structure Model.	
• 1.3 CS Hubs Operating Model.	
• 1.4 CS Hubs' participatory R&I activities	
• 1.5 Methodological guide and toolkit for setting up CS Hubs.	
• 1.6 Action Plan & roadmap for the setup of CS Hubs	
• 2.1 Code of conduct defining the rights and obligations of parties involved in the activities of the CS hubs, addressing ethical and legal considerations.	
• 3.1 Memorandum of Collaboration of CS Hubs with quadruple helix stakeholders.	
• 3.2 CS Hub Stakeholder Board and Board of Directors	
• 3.3 CS Hub Facilitator, Community Managers, Trainers	
• 4.1 RRI regulations and standards across RRI keys.	
• 4.2 Adoption of the 10 Principles of Citizen Science	
• 4.3 Research ethics & integrity regulations of CS Hub.	
• 5.1 Citizen Science Hub societal, democratic, economic and scientific impact assessment methodology.	
• 6.1 Development of capacity building content for active participation in citizen science.	
• 7.1 Adoption of gender balance measures about CS Hub staff power.	
• 7.2 Adoption of gender balance standards for participation in CS Hubs' activities.	
• 7.3 Adoption of Inclusive incentivisation methodology for participation in CS Hubs.	
• 8.1 Open access provisions for the operation of CS Hubs (e.g. use of open data repositories, open source software, etc.).	
• 9.1 Material for stakeholders' capacity building.	
• 9.2 Framework for Stakeholders' Mutual learning.	
• 9.3 Methodology for engagement of Quadruple Helix Actors.	
• 10.1 Memorandum of Collaboration between CS Hubs.	
• 10.2 Network of Interest in institutionalisation of CS Hubs and grounding RRI in regional communities.	

8. Apart from the above, did your RPFO recently **undertake any other initiatives** (e.g., institutional changes) to embed Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) practices into its governance framework and research activities? If yes, then could you please describe them? *Examples of such initiatives could be (i) the adoption of new forms of decision-making; (ii) employing methodologies for a more meaningful public engagement; and (iii) measures to ensure shared responsibility and ownership of the introduced changes.*

9. (O24.5) How hard has it been (or is expected to be) to **promote institutional changes** that foster RRI within your RPFO?

Very easy

Very hard

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10

10. According to your opinion, which have been (or expected to be) the **key barriers** and challenges to embodying RRI practices in your RPFO’s governance framework and research activities?

11. (O24.6) How hard has it been to **collect the information** and data asked in this report?

Very easy

Very hard

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10

12. Which are the **key barriers** and challenges to collecting the information and data asked in this report? *Particularly mention those indicators (questions) that were the hardest and, potentially, you failed to collect the required information. Also, please mention if you think that the current report could be adapted in any way to monitor institutional changes better.*

Finally, if you wish, you are welcome to add any other indicators that you would like to monitor.

#	Indicator / Question	Data
13		
14		
15		

ABOUT THE PROJECT

INCENTIVE aims to demonstrate the potential of citizen science through the co-creation, establishment and assessment of Citizen Science Hubs in four EU Universities: University of Twente (NL), Autonomous University of Barcelona (ES), Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (EL) and Vilnius Gediminas Technical University (LT).

By doing so, the project accelerates the transition of these institutions to more inclusive, open and democratic innovation and scientific governance, under the principles of Responsible Research and Innovation. The project seeks to deliver a legacy to European and international research institutes on how to create and operate their own Hub with the aim to secure a sustainable future.

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